

A STUDY ON EFFICACY OF EMPLOYEE TRAINING: REVIEW OF LITERATURE

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Abstract. The success of any organization depends on appropriate use of human assets available in the organization. All other assets could only be supplementary to human assets. Towards augmenting the human resources and to cope with changes – both internal and external, the organization has to concentrate necessarily on developing the ability, wisdom and skills of its workforce. For the development of human asset, ‘training’ becomes the base. Training is a tool to attain individual, organizational needs related to the jobs undertaken and is also intended to improve the work culture of the group involved in a group task. An ideal training programme can be expected to change the attitude, skills and develop forward vision of the participants towards the task. This paper summarizes the results of the literature review on the effectiveness of training programmes of employees from diverse perspective.

Keywords: training, learning, organization, group, individual, effectiveness.

JEL Classification: M53.

DARBUOTOJŲ MOKYMŲ EFEKTYVUMO TYRIMAI: LITERATŪROS APŽVALGA

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Santrauka. Bet kurios organizacijos sėkmė priklauso nuo žmogiškųjų išteklių. Visi kiti organizacijos ištekliai gali būti tik priderinami prie žmogiškųjų. Siekiant sustiprinti žmogiškuosius išteklius ir susidoroti su pokyčiais – tiek vidaus, tiek išorės, organizacijai būtina plėtoti savo darbuotojų žinias ir gebėjimus. Siekiant šio tikslo, mokymai tampa itin reikšmingi. Mokymai – tai priemonė patenkinti individualius, organizacinius poreikius, susijusius su darbo vieta, be to, tai priemonė, kuri orientuota gerinti grupės darbo kultūrą sprendžiant užduotis grupiniu režimu. Racionalios mokymo programos leidžia keisti požiūrį (nuostatas), plėtoti įgūdžius ir nukreipto dalyvius užduoties link. Šiame straipsnyje apibendrinami atlikti tyrimai apie darbuotojų mokymo programų veiksmingumą įvairių perspektyvų atžvilgiu.

Reikšminiai žodžiai: mokymas, organizavimas, grupė, individualus, efektyvumas, mokymasis.

1. Introduction

The Workers or Employees working in or for an organization are now being considered as 'human assets' even though different terms like 'staff', 'manpower', 'personnel', etc. are still in currency. The emerging trend is to treat them as 'human assets' or 'human resources'. The success of any organization depends on appropriate use of human assets available in the organization. All other assets could only be supplementary to human assets. Towards augmenting the human resources and to cope with changes – both internal and external, the organization has to concentrate necessarily on developing the ability, wisdom and skills of its workforce. The training effectiveness is dependent on two considerations, (1) Trainers are fully responsible for training and if the employees do not show results, the trainer should be held accountable (2) Training effectiveness depends on the kind of atmosphere and culture that is prevalent back at home (Mehta 1970). Training programmes should focus on corporate planning, organizational development and personnel management (Srinivasan 1977).

Constant changes take place in the internal and external levels of business units. It is necessary for the organization to restructure and reinforce the human assets to adapt itself to changes. Business does not have unanimous methodologies for evaluation and it depends on suitability (Bivainis, Morkvenas 2008). It is of paramount importance to any organization to strive for the development of its employees as esteemed members of the organizational management team. For the development of human asset, 'training' becomes the base. Training is a tool to attain individual, organizational needs related to the jobs undertaken and is also intended to improve the work culture of the group involved in a group task. An ideal training programme can be expected to change the attitude, skill and develop forward vision of the participants towards the task. This paper summarizes the results of the literature review on the effectiveness of training programmes of employees from diverse perspective.

The study has the following objectives:

1. To evaluate the pre- training arrangements, need identification methods and their operational utility.
2. To analyze the effectiveness of training programmes on self- need attainment.
3. To evaluate the effect of the training programmes on group dynamism, group performance and group needs.
4. To evaluate the impact of training programmes on organizational needs and goals.

The study aims to analyze the developments and impact of in-built training programmes carried out on the basis of pre-training arrangements, which will normally be in a sequential order. It also aims to study the impact of programmes on various levels of workforce – employees, supervisors and executives vary according to their age and educational qualifications.

The data have been collected by administering a questionnaire for pre- and post- training evaluation along with pre- and post- wrote test based on the syllabus of training that have been collected from the sampled programmes. Opinions have been collected by using evaluation questionnaires for different level-executives, supervisors and employees. Using a modified questionnaire, opinions have been collected from training coordinators since these training coordinators are the link between the training center (in built) and various departments of the organization. Thus the study is based on more than one method of data collection.

Study of jobs and skill analysis is necessary. The training thus imparted would help the employees to adjust to their job requirements (Dayal 1970). Training needs for supervisors need to be identified through careful observations, which indicate poor performance, low production, high cost, poor product quality, high scrap, spoilage, wastage, accidents, absenteeism, and turnover (Sundaram 1970). While Building knowledge – based society and economy, particular importance in human Resources management fall on the value of human resources and management expertise (Lobanova 2009).

The day-to-day complaints and grievances also form a useful source for identifying their training needs. There are some ideologies for training methodologies, which are the bases for training effectiveness. Multinational operating in India finds that their home- tested techniques do not have the same impact here. Due to differences in culture and background business games, T-groups, case methods and workshops are not as effective in India as perhaps in Europe or America. He ends that given the Indian context, the lecture- cum- discussion method would be more useful (Basha 1971).

Structured exercises seem to offer greater scope in India. Techniques such as T-group, management games assume a minimum level of intellectual competence in the participants. The trainer therefore has the additional responsibility of selecting right methodology (Prahlaad, Thiagarajan 1971). Organizational Development (OD) technique can be more useful for training employees in government sector. The training programme of the government is designed to inculcate capabilities to introduce change and review the environment (Saxena 1973).

The data have been collected from supervisors who had undergone training in an Indian Engineering Company. They have administered a checklist for the collection of data. The response showed that the inputs in industrial relations have little or no impact on their effectiveness. However, most of them thought that training did improve their self-confidence, motivation, identification with the management goals, communication ability and skill (Banerji 1981). The data have been collected from 999 respondents from banking institutions. Though these managers found training programmes

less effective with respect to their contributions to job performance, they did endorse the usefulness of formal training (Maheswari 1981). A shift from knowledge to attitude is the main objective of training and identifies three areas of training: technical, skills and knowledge. He suggests that the emphasis on these three must vary according to the levels of the employees (Bhatia 1981).

A study on graduate engineering trainees in three large Public Sector Organizations found that the trainees perceived both the method and contents of the training as demotivating and dissatisfying (Agarwal 1982). Training for personnel managers should be directed towards attitudes and beliefs underlying managerial philosophy and their inter relatedness (Seth 1984).

The need for behavioural inputs is vital in any training programme organized for supervisors (Ghosh 1984). The study is evaluating management training and development deals with pre-training evaluation. The study includes evaluation of training context, input evaluation, post-training evaluation, transfer of learning and job improvement. The study is suggested for job evaluation as a follow-up after six months to one year. All these aspects have been evaluated for the executives training programme organized in the 'Administrative Staff College', Hyderabad, which brings out the impact of institutional programmes (Virmani, Seth 1985). Two models have been suggested to evaluate training effectiveness. First is the expectation achievement model consisting of matching post-training achievement with pre-training expectation of the boss, peers, the sub-ordinates and trainee himself. The second is the experimental control group model where a group of employees who have gone through training is compared in terms of their performance with those who have not (Sikka 1985).

The data have been collected from 119 managers in the steel industry who had attended training in a company or external training programmes. A questionnaire has been administered and responses are tallied. Most respondents were found to be satisfied with the instructors, the size of training group, the training duration, the reading material and the training equipment. They all thought that the environment did help in carrying out some of the learning that took place during training (Jain 1985). In the work-Evaluation methodology for training based on various research findings of Food and Agricultural Organizations of United Nations, recommended systematic evaluation for 'agricultural training' programmes is organized by agriculture extension agencies. Andhra Pradesh State Electricity Board evaluated particularly growth, organization structure and problems in achieving managerial performance. It has brought out objectives of training and course content, method followed for effective training in service undertaking (Bhatnagar 1987).

Human resource Development in Public Enterprise dealt with a conceptual analysis of Human Resource Development, organizational development, performance

appraisal and carrier development of Steel Authority of India Limited (Bansal 1991). In the study on HRD practices in Indian industries a comparative study of BHEL and National Fertilizers Limited was made with various Human Resource Development concepts, objectives and practices and considered training as a sub-system (Jain 1996).

The previous studies based on institutional training programmes do not evaluate how they benefit to the industries concerned. The institutional training programmes do not concentrate on future needs of individual organizations, which vary in environment and production process. So, the environmental condition among the centers of learning and applications of learning are not homogeneous. Further, the impact of training depends on the caliber of the participants, which varies from individual to individual.

In the last two decades, organization has increasingly used computer-based instruction as a method to deliver training to employees and instruction to students (Huang 2010).

Training expenses represent a substantial investment in human resource (Eichmann 2009). Performance and attitudinal outcomes were generally examined across four training designs: classroom training only, classroom training with self-coaching, classroom training with multi-source feedback and classroom training with self-coaching and multi-source feedback (Kules 2008). The effectiveness of e-learning in the industrial setting at Level three is based on the Kirkpatrick model and compared to traditional classroom learning (Tews 2006). Effectiveness was determined by assessing the transfer skills from training to the job (Yaw 2005): to determine the impact of a management development program on organizational performance and to evaluate the influence of management relations on union grievance filing rates (Bostain 2000). The development and application of a checklist for evaluating e-learning in organizations is based on Scriven's Key Evaluation Checklist (Guidy-Oulai 2009).

2. Pre-training arrangement process

A systematic pre-training arrangement process is necessary for the success of any training programme. It is of utmost importance that the pre-training arrangement should be planned and arranged in a sequential order. This process will consist of various elements like training need identification, selection of right participants and imparting training through an appropriate method with proper application of training techniques. The training need identification and selection of participants are the two interdependent elements of the 'planning part'. The adoption of suitable methods and appropriate techniques belong to the 'execution part'.

The two parts of the pre-training process are connected with Training coordinators. Any lapse or failure in one part of the process is bound to affect the other part also. The acceptance and suitability of methods and techniques

should be evaluated by the participants. For this, feedback information from the participants and from the training coordinators is necessary. On the basis of the feedback from participants, the techniques and methods should be changed to make the programmes trainee-centered. The training need identification helps to find out 'actual needs' or 'genuine needs' of training and this step is aimed to benefit the trainees ultimately. By a proper identification of the training needs, mere 'course attending' by participants and their sense of simple 'relaxation from job' could be eliminated, that is to say the participants are made to involve themselves totally in the programme seriously and sincerely. Through need identification process, the persons who are in real need are nominated and thus the training becomes 'need based'. Several earlier studies have stressed the importance of need identification and have brought out that any lapse on this part may affect the entire system of training. Different persons can help to determine the needs for a development programme. They are top management in the organization, staff personnel in the organization such as personnel managers, development and industrial engineers, supervisors, subordinates to be trained, outsiders such as consultants, psychologists, research specialists and training and development specialists (Kirkpatrick 1983).

The willingness to attend the training programme depends on the knowledge acquisition, skill development, attitudinal and behavioural modification or changes. The willingness of the individuals, that is, when trainees are induced by self-motivation, controlling officer and section heads.

3. Teaching methods

Training depends to a large extent on teaching and teaching in turn depends on various methods of instruction. Instruction by the trainer can be made through different methods; medium and the effectiveness of training depend on the most suitable one for a particular programme. The trainer or instructor must find the best combination of various teaching methods that meet the needs or objectives of the programme. So, the right selection of teaching method becomes more essential for effective training.

Training techniques

The success of training depends to a large extent on the 'presentation'. The 'presentation' means the actual training techniques. The learning ability of individuals differs with person to person. The ability to learn and learning depend on various techniques like material presentation during training, study environment and motivation during training. The learning during training will have a negative result, when the material presented becomes more difficult or not related to the training. Fatigue or boredom during the programme also affects the performance.

Training Need Assessment (TNA) is based on 'reactive' or 'proactive' factors. A reactive TNA occurs when the perceived performance deficiency is a discrepancy between perceived and expected performance of employee's current job. A proactive TNA is conducted to respond to the perception that current job behaviour reflects the inability to meet future standards or expectations. It is for development purposes (Camp *et al.* 1986). Identification of training needs is the stepping-stone on which entire training is built. An organization employs a person with sufficient knowledge, effective performance needs and certain competence. But due to some reasons, existing performance becomes sluggish and short. The process of assessing and finding the gap between standard competence and existing competence in terms of knowledge, skill and attitude are called as identification of training needs. These views have taken a comprehensive process of identifying training needs assessment and have described the process of identifying training under the two situations- ideal and less than ideal (Sah 1991).

Need assessment under ideal situations consists of steps to take an inventory of present manpower, to make forecast of future requirements, to find the people needed and to decide what to do, how to develop manpower. The process under less than ideal situations include stages such as considering terms of reference, considering the information available in respect of new and existing employees, considering the problems which arise within the organizations and considering possible approaches like observation, management request, interviews, job analysis, questionnaire survey, performing ratings and tests (Stayton 1985).

A study covering 24 organizations, of which 18 belong to private sector and six public sectors, showed that 33% of public sector units followed only the adhoc methods and did not adapt any scientific method for identifying training need. However in the private sector, only 12% of the organizations resorted to adhoc decisions. Between the various methods, public sector favoured performance appraisal, and individual personal interviews are favoured in private sector units (Virmani, Seth 1985). It is also substantiated through a survey-cum-experimental study conducted with 400 supervisory groups – All India Service Officers of Uttar Pradesh Government concluded that the new training policy in 1985, which replaced existing adhoc arrangements, is neither a part of a new developmental paradigm nor based on need assessment (Sanwal 1988). The objectives and content of the development input can be better outlined and validated if planned after discussions with representative sample of administrator in the senior category (Saxena 1973).

The contribution of faculty, materials presented and other teaching apparatus used constitute the techniques of training which results in:

(i) Acquiring or sharpening the capabilities to perform various tasks or functions.

(ii) Developing general individual capabilities for development purpose.

(iii) Developing group and organizational culture. The impact of training is influenced by the extent as well as the type of training technique and the material intended for imparting training. The respondents who underwent training best adjust to the effectiveness and quality of training technique. The evaluation of the training technique by the employees have been executed by five different components such as:

(i) Material presented related to their job functions.

(ii) Material presented related to solve the day-to-day problems.

(iii) Ratings regarding the faculty and overall teaching techniques.

(iv) Visual aids and other teaching apparatus evaluation.

(v) Whether programme objective is consistent with organizational objective?

Now the study is proposed to examine the impact of the three components of training goals which are:

(i) Self- goals.

(ii) Organizational goal and

(iii) Group dynamism.

The efficacy of training can be concluded when the above three needs that are individual, organization and group needs are fulfilled.

4. Impact of training on self- needs attainment

The success of any organization is determined by the commitment of its workforce, their caliber and aptitude towards the task. The total and sincere involvement of human asset is the only resource, which is capable of self-propulsion and value addition. For other business assets there may be depreciation over the years of use, whereas the human asset appreciates over the years of experience. It is an asset with the gathered knowledge, experience and skill that helps to tackle the problems and paves the way for innovation. Unless people are developed and kept satisfied there will be an adverse result. Even though the organization addresses to its development constantly, the employee's initiative for self-development is the base. Every person in an organization is an independent entity having his own ideas and sense of values. Each one in the organization has own ego, urge for survival and a desire for development. In fulfilling the objectives of the organization, he is also pursuing his individual objectives. It would not be wrong to state that basically people come to work to achieve their own self-needs and objectives and in this process ultimately, the organization gets benefited.

If an organization effectively develops its human resources, it automatically enhances the performance and productivity. Before analyzing the impact of training on self, it is necessary to bring out the important aspects of 'self needs'. Actually the individual needs and the organization needs

are not independent, but interdependent. "The relationship between organizational and individual goals can be identified by exploring what individuals want from the organization and what the organization wants from the individuals". But human behavior is a complex phenomenon and is affected by many factors. In the course of redesigning and reinforcing the workforce, the management with appropriate training should make the people understand the present objectives and channelize the ability for the future. With this view the constantly changing environment, the skills acquired in the academic institutions, no longer provides a guarantee for future advancement for middle-aged employees. Technical obsolescence is one reason for deteriorating job performance. Individuals must look beyond the advancement into the future, each individual must recognize and develop the applicability of the skills and techniques in appropriate problem, situation or condition. They must also expect change and accept it as a challenge, the organization must develop suitable training to meet future eventualities and also favourable opportunities should be created.

Individuals differ substantially in the abilities as far as the work environment is concerned. It becomes necessary to shape the ability for changing job environment through training and development. To do the required job, intellectual ability, inherent intelligence and psychomotor ability that includes physical abilities to perform the works are to be coordinated. Matching of abilities of employees with job requires effective training and development

5. Impact of training on group needs and group dynamism

'Groups' gain more importance for the basic reason that they will carry out the task more effectively than as individuals and this results in the overall organizational objective attainment. But at the same time, 'groups' are composed of individuals who have different identities, which focus on their attitudes towards the group task. For the effectiveness of the group work, they must be focused on the main task and co-ordinated towards group culture. This may be done through proper need- based training.

Group is 'two or more who interact with each other in such a manner that each person influences and is influenced by one another' (Shaw 1917). Group theory is based on activities, interactions and sentiments. Persons in a group interact with each other, not in just the physical propinquity sense but also to solve problems, attain goals, ease co-ordination, reduce tension and achieve a balance (Homans 1950). Group theory also states that people are attracted to each other because of similar attitudes towards commonly relevant objects and goals (Newcomb 1961).

Cohesive co-ordinated behaviour results in promotion of group culture. This group culture promotes adoptability. Adoptability motivates to achieve a common goal. Group

culture ends in the formation of effective teamwork. To encourage and develop team spirit within individuals, their behaviour should be modified. Behaviour modification is one important aspect of training. So training programmes dealt with group situation, team building aspects, counseling skills may develop a cohesive group and it is more important in a manufacturing unit where the work is almost a group process. Effective team spirit is the essence of group culture and must be developed among individuals, which is determined by several aspects. An effective team spirit, which is formulated by the committed team members, and its success depends on their performance, concern for other individuals and supportive communication. Several factors can tilt individuals and groups towards either competition or co-operation. Some factors lie in the characteristics of individuals, some in the group composition and dynamics and other in the nature of the task or environment of the group (Jewell, Reitz 1981). Persons in a group interact with each other, not in just the physical propinquity sense but also to solve problems, attain goals, ease co-ordination, reduce tension and achieve a balance (Scott 1967).

An ideal participation of all members in the group task or project must be motivated towards goal achievement. The goals are established by organization and it must be matched with individuals and group goals. The commitment of individuals must be developed to attain the team goal. 'Goal modification' results in pooling of knowledge, abilities of different members, which reorients in resource expertise. For the group task with persons of different objectives, pre-determined goals, planned action, clear visions are essential. The clear vision of group culture makes sharing of their knowledge, values and purpose with their colleagues. This also depends on their communication skills. The communication skills are essential because 'groups' are nothing but individuals with the team spirit who share the common goal or interact among individuals to achieve the standard task performance. Information sharing forms the base of group culture. The interaction of people within a group depends on the behaviour of individuals within the group.

Several factors can tilt individuals and groups towards either competition or co-operation. In a group work the role clarity between the members is also essential. The role of each individual must be clear and their importance must be tied towards group goals. Training helps to replace old values by new norms like enlarged vision and role clarity. It has become a tool to develop workforce and sustain them in the organization. All the above aspects create an effective group and this is possible by training the members of the group to achieve pre-determined objectives. Training is a process, which eases the individuals to act collectively. Employees from different functional areas form into a task group for a project to attain the organizational objective. As this task group crosses the departmental barriers, it also promotes democracy in the organizational environment.

Other than being an employee with direct work commitment, group needs and group dynamism will make the workforce to involve in decision making by active participation of each group. This participation, involvement, if promoted between workforces, will improve the quality and quantity of work. The formulation of effective group behaviour is not so easy because the group behaviour is affected by the personality. The opportunities for interaction, role clarity, cohesiveness, motive to adhere to group norms are the basis of group dynamism. Individuals, by working together and by pooling their resource abilities, can effectively accomplish their shared goals. Though group work is an effective one, to organize an effective group is difficult. Educational system, workmanship, social status, personal traits and other individual needs often divert individuals to be away from group task. Moreover, individuals act, feel and think differently. Eventually for every human attribute, there are practical individual differences. As individuals are different, complications or conflicts may arise because they want to be treated as unique. Although people inherit certain individual characteristics and tendencies, continuous training results in 'behavioural differentiation'. This will make the individuals adoptable to the 'group task'. The two fundamental dimensions for effective 'group task' are the promotion of group culture and group dynamism.

Identical individual behaviour is essential for group task accomplishment. So co-ordination of individuals and developing a cohesive group becomes essential. Cohesiveness promotes strong drive for common goal attainment. Group dynamics refers to the study of forces operating within a group and it describes how a group should be organized and operated. It also refers to how individual members, other groups and the organization are affected. It also denotes various techniques for promotion of effective groups. The inter-departmental interaction and relationship depend on communication skill and behaviour modification, which are the pre-requisites of group dynamism (Davis 1997).

The group needs in development programmes are organized to promote group efforts at various levels of workforce, dissolving all the differences and committed to reach the goals. Without unanimity of vision and commitment to the goals between the various levels of workforce, there can be no appreciable results.

6. Impact of training on organization needs

Assessment of the employee's knowledge potential for education, vocational experience, position level, decision acceptance degree and responsibility, self-sufficiency at work, work culture, technology used at work, work difficulty level, motivation and worker's influence on reaching organization objectives is essential.

The appropriate training and familiarizing employees with possible hazards in the job and with practices, methods

will minimize the likelihood of their having accidents and develop proper attitudes towards job (Surry 1968).

Measurement of training includes a comprehensive measurement of training organization, expenditure, duration, process and delivery methods. The firms with sophisticated training system and strong management support are most successful at maximizing the effectiveness of their training (Tung-Chun Huang 2001).

The training and education can affect the organizational performance by two ways. The first is means of increase in knowledge and skills, which improves customer satisfaction. The second is the staff retention, which is underpinned by staff satisfaction.

Each organization has an internal environment but also exists in an external environment. The internal environment is in terms of task, structure, technology, social and economic variables, while the external environment is in terms of the larger social, political, economic and cultural factors. To function effectively, organization has to achieve equilibrium with the environmental factors. In an organization, a change in environment is inevitable. The organization that does not change or keep pace with the changing environment suffers and tends to be defunct. Changes occur in almost all organizations due to:

- Technological innovations.
- Competition.
- Advancement of communication and other information systems.
- Updating of management techniques and industrial innovations.

The organization faces many challenges due to above changes, all these make the organization to be a learning organization. It has become an accepted fact that beside money, material and machines, the success of any organization depends on the quality of human resources. The training programmes are to promote organization needs and achieve organizational goals in a process. The goals of the organization are both qualitative and quantitative. Both these aspects have been concentrated on employees and supervisors level and the result of performance change due to training has been evaluated. The qualitative organization need attained by executives due to training results in effective planning and development. They do not participate in direct quantitative task. Organizational development programme has pre-determined objectives to sharpen the capabilities in various functions. The participants are able to improve their performance and achieve the organizational goals with respect to cost effectiveness cost reduction and quality appreciation.

7. Conclusions

The previous studies based on institutional training programmes do not evaluate how they benefit to the industries

concerned. The institutional training programmes do not concentrate on future needs of individual organizations, which vary in environment and production process. So, the environmental condition among the centers of learning and applications of learning are not homogeneous. Further, the impact of training depends on the caliber of the participants, which varies from individual to individual.

The previous studies carried out have evaluated the impact of training on the level of workforce that is 'executives' or 'management trainees' or 'students of management' level only. Thus it may be the impact of managerial caliber of that level of workforce but in a manufacturing unit, most of the works are 'group work' which needs smooth 'work culture' of total workforce. The training programmes of Government units are different where the administrative rules are guiding factors. So, the participants will not freely express the impact of training and the evaluation may be an incomplete one.

Thus, the current study deals with the pre-training arrangements process and explains the interdependent elements of 'planning part' consisting of training need identification and selection of right participants, the 'execution part' which is composed of suitable methods and appropriate techniques. Training coordinators link the two parts of training process. This sequential arrangement is analyzed and then the impacts of training on self- needs attainment are considered. The details regarding self-goals towards training, advancement of knowledge by training and performance change of self due to training for the levels of employees and supervisors has been studied. The skill development, individual and self-actualization needs due to training for the executives have also been studied.

Thus, the impacts of training on group performance change in the levels of employees and supervisors. Group needs for executives have also been studied. The study also discusses the impact of training on organization needs in the light of the above-mentioned objectives, which gives a comprehensive approach to training evaluation.

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